

Training And Athlete Injuries

Training Information

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Abstract

Upon examining the many explanations and meanings of the word training, it becomes evident that concepts such as physical performance, high efficiency, health, and planning are crucial to its understanding. It is necessary to consolidate all these words and formulate the following definition; All systematic and organized efforts aimed at optimizing performance via monitoring the athlete's well-being are referred to as training. If the athlete is trained with a

"success at all costs" mentality and handled like a "racehorse," he will jeopardize his health, rendering the achieved results insignificant. Consequently, the athlete's health should take precedence. We need to cultivate both a healthy individual and a well-trained athlete. The Objectives of Training The primary objective of the coach is to optimize the athlete's potential and enhance performance to the highest standard. To do this, certain objectives must be attained throughout training. It is advisable to examine these.

Keywords: Training, Athlete Injuries, Athlete, Training Information, Athlete Training

Introduction

- 1. Attaining and cultivating comprehensive physical development: Each sport has shared characteristics that need enhancement.** Essential attributes such as overall strength, endurance, flexibility, speed, and coordination, necessary in almost all athletic disciplines, should be cultivated to achieve a harmoniously balanced physique.
- 2. Cultivating specific physical and motor attributes essential for the respective sport:** Given that the characteristics and requirements of each sport may vary, it is imperative to identify and refine these through the development of specialized endurance, flexibility, strength (including explosive strength), balance, and coordination. Consequently, the athlete should be capable of executing his tasks without sustaining injuries due to the conducted training sessions.
- 3. Refining and enhancing technique: Technique represents the most efficient and effective method for an athlete to execute an action.** Prior to attaining elite athlete status, an individual must dedicate sufficient time to training in order to master the optimal techniques of their sport, which should be personalized and refined to suit the athlete's capabilities.
- 4. Formulating a plan for the sport:** Another objective is to establish the tactics and strategy to be used by analyzing the attributes of our players, the traits of our opponents, and the strategies they utilize in various competitions.

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5. Implementing essential safeguards to avert injuries: *The coach must fortify the muscles, tendons, and ligaments of the players to mitigate injury risk. He endeavors to maintain optimal field conditions, equipment, and other things that might potentially lead to injuries.*

6. Safeguarding the athlete's health: *Athletes should, if feasible, receive yearly health examinations, and their well-being should be prioritized. The primary objective of our efforts should be to cultivate healthy persons, with all other aims relegated to secondary importance.*

7. Cultivation of willpower: *attaining the will and capacity to surmount training challenges, discipline in training and conduct, and embodying traits such as bravery, persistence, and a competitive spirit.*

8. Fostering team cohesion: *Solidarity, camaraderie, and a positive social environment within the squad are key concerns for the coach to cultivate. Athletes should recognize that they are part of a collective working towards a common objective, rather than functioning alone.*

9. Furnishing the athlete with comprehensive knowledge and updates on the sport's regulations: *Ongoing theoretical instruction by the coach serves as an additional training objective.*

Aim, Methodology and Findings

GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT TRAINING

1- What is performance?

The effectiveness in physiological, biomechanical, and psychological aspects necessary for a physical activity is termed "performance." The extent to which this efficiency is shown during competition also indicates the degree of performance.

2- What are the elements that constitute performance?

According to Astrand and Rodalha, the elements that constitute the performance are grouped under three main headings. These are as follows:

a-Energy production (aerobic-anaerobic),

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b-Neuro-muscular (nerve-muscle) transmission,

c-Psychological factors (motivation)

3-What are the factors affecting performance?

Various factors affect performance. These factors are primarily divided into two categories: internal and external factors.

Internal factors include:

- a. Training level,
- b. Age,
- c. Gender.
- d. Physical fitness,
- e. Racial factors,
- f. Stress level,
- g. Motivation status
- h. Nutrition,
- i. Ergonomic supports,
- j. Health status,
- k. Drug use

External factors or external factors are as follows:

- a. Altitude,
- b. Humidity

c. Temperature,

d. Ground condition

The factors listed above affect performance positively or negatively depending on their situation.

4- What is training?

It encompasses all research focused on enhancing sports performance aspects within a structured program to attain specific performance objectives within a defined system. Physiologists characterize training in the following manner: Functional and morphological adaptation to all imposed stressors on the body, resulting in physiological changes and eventually enhanced efficiency. Another definition of training is as follows: Preparation of athletes in physical, technical, tactical, mental, psychological, and motor aspects via workouts.

5-What are the effects of training?

Through proper and methodical training, all performance components may be enhanced. Training enhances the energy production system. Consequently, the cardiovascular system is enhanced by exercise, resulting in an improvement in the athlete's aerobic capacity. Fatigue resistance improves. Neuro-muscular transmission is enhanced by training. Strength has been enhanced. Coordination and flexibility are enhanced. Attributes such as mobility and proficiency are enhanced. Furthermore, the athlete's technical, tactical, cerebral, and psychological attributes also evolve. In summary, training may enhance athletes' energy production systems, strength, and motor qualities.

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6- What is aerobic energy production?

It is the organism's oxygen energy production mechanism. At the cellular level, oxygen transported by the blood metabolizes energy-providing molecules. The human body is primarily a living entity that exists in an aerobic environment. The breathed air occupies the alveoli of the lungs. The alveoli are encircled by capillaries like a spider's web. In this context, hemoglobin, an iron-containing protein present in blood within capillaries that imparts a red hue to erythrocytes, interacts with oxygen from the alveoli (air sacs) through diffusion (movement from a region of lower concentration to one of higher concentration), resulting in the formation of oxyhemoglobin. This chemical is delivered to the heart via the bloodstream, which then pumps it to the cellular level. It delivers it to the cellular level. At the cellular level, hemoglobin binds with carbon dioxide, releases oxygen, and returns to the heart, facilitating the purification of deoxygenated blood. Oxygen reaches the cellular level, combusting energy-providing molecules, mostly carbohydrates (sugars), resulting in the formation of energy (ATP) via the aerobic route.

7- How to develop aerobic power?

Diverse training methods have been established to enhance the aerobic capacity, referred to as endurance in this context, of the human body, specifically targeting the oxygen energy generation systems. These approaches are often categorized under the following principal headings:

a-Marathon type training: This involves relatively slow long distance running (or swimming, depending on the type of sport).

b-Interval training: Interval training, also known as interval training, is the training method that develops athletes' aerobic power most quickly. Interval training has four basic elements. These are distance, interval, tempo and repetition number, respectively.

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c-Fartleks: In this type of training, also called tempo running, athletes make various ascents and descents on rough terrain for a minimum of 30-45 minutes.

8- What is anaerobic energy production?

It is the anaerobic energy generation mechanism of the body. It has two components: the ATP-CP system (alaxide) and the lactic acid system (lactacid). Initially, the readily available ATP (adenosine triphosphate) inside the muscle cell is used throughout all muscular activity. In the absence of sufficient oxygen in the environment, energy-providing compounds undergo anaerobic combustion. Upon completion of this procedure, a by-product known as lactic acid (milk acid) is produced. This system is sometimes referred to as the lactic acid system.

9- How to develop anaerobic power?

The anaerobic capacity of the human body is often more challenging to enhance than aerobic capacity. Two points serve as the first reference. The points are supramaximal loads and the repeating technique. Particularly with supramaximal loads and repetition methods, the organism's tolerance to lactic acid is enhanced. These loads are briefer than the continuous loading approach, but more intense.

10- What is steady state?

Steady state refers to the condition in which the energy necessary for a physical activity is supplied, and the intake and use of oxygen are equilibrated. During physical exertion, a linear escalation in heart rate is seen to accommodate the activity. The rise ceases upon reaching a stable state, when heart rate is equilibrated and fluctuations are reduced. The equilibrium of oxygen intake and expenditure is under consideration. Physiologists generally agree that an organism attains a steady state when the variation in heart rate falls below 5 beats per minute.

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11- How to count heart beats (pulse)?

The heart rate is often measured at two intervals during training. The sites are the arterioadialis in the wrist and the arteriocarotid in the neck. The heart rate is typically measured for one minute, starting at zero. Nevertheless, due to a reduction in heart rate occurring within one minute during training, heart rate is often measured over a duration of 10 or 15 seconds. When 10 seconds elapse, the resultant number is multiplied by 6; when 15 seconds elapse, the resultant number is multiplied by 4. It is important to note that there will be a margin of error of +6 for a duration of 10 seconds, and +4 for a duration of 15 seconds.

12- Which energy formation is effective in which branch of sports?

Numerous researchers have identified useful energy production techniques in sports. All energy production mechanisms are used during physical exercise. However, the critical aspect here is determining which option is most effective. Currently, sporting disciplines are categorized into several classes based on their energy production mechanisms. The anaerobic energy generation approach is successful for activities lasting one minute or less when assessed by duration. In the context of team sports such as football, basketball, volleyball, and handball, the operations of both formation systems are under examination. Anaerobic energy production is very active during sprints executed in rapid assaults in football, basketball, or handball. Following these sprints, players transition into jogs, moving from the defensive zone to the offensive zone, where aerobic energy production is engaged during non-rapid dribbling. The energy formation mechanisms used in sporting competitions are interconnected. They are used in conjunction. However, when assessing these team sports based on time, the aerobic engagement of 2 x 45 minutes of football, 2 x 20 minutes of basketball, and 2 x 30 minutes of handball should not be contested.

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13- How many types of muscles are there?

The human body has three kinds of muscles. There are three types of muscle: smooth muscle, striated muscle, and cardiac muscle. Smooth muscle is classified as an involuntary muscle. These muscles are situated around our internal organs. Striated muscles are muscles that contract voluntarily. Cardiac muscle is a unique kind of muscle that resembles striated muscle but functions like smooth muscle.

14-Does the number of muscle fibers increase?

The quantity of muscle fibers remains constant from birth. The muscle hypertrophies at a certain pace contingent upon the exercise regimen. The muscular mass increases. This phenomenon is referred to as hypertrophy. The increase in mass results from the hypertrophy of individual muscle fibers, leading to a greater quantity of myofibrils. Another cause for hypertrophy is the observation of a specific tension wave when the central nervous system (CNS) engages in the contraction. Hettinger asserts that each 2mc muscle is capable of lifting 6 kg of weight. Consequently, when the muscle's cross-sectional area enlarges, the force it generates correspondingly escalates. The quantity of muscle fibers does not grow. In 1975, Goldberg and his colleagues established that the cross-section of muscle fibers bifurcates when attaining a certain value. This process is referred to as hyperplasia.

15-What are the common features of muscles?

Muscles have five common characteristics. These characteristics are:

- a. Arousability,
- b. Ability to communicate
- c. Contractility,
- d. Being elastic,

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e. It should be a viscous mass.

Muscles, like all living tissues, react to applied stimuli. This reply is presented as a contraction. Muscles are typically activated by neural stimulation. They possess the capability to convey this stimulation. A muscle reacts to stimuli by contracting. When we attempt to extend a muscle beyond its resting length, we experience resistance; upon cessation of the stretching action, the muscle reverts to its original length. This pertains to the characteristic of flexibility. The muscle exhibits resistance because to internal friction against the force attempting to alter its form. A equilibrium is attained between these two forces throughout time.

16-What is Force?

The concept of strength is defined differently throughout several scientific disciplines. In the realm of athletics, the capacity to overcome opposition is termed strength.

17-How many types of forces are there?

There are three categories of strength. These include maximum strength (unit strength, brute strength, fundamental strength), fast strength, and strength endurance.

18-What is maximal strength?

Maximal strength is the highest level of force a person can exert simultaneously. In other words, it is the maximum weight that may be raised by the voluntary contraction of the neuromuscular system. Maximal strength may be integrated with speed in sprinting and long jumps, as well as with endurance in rowing.

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19-What does maximal strength depend on?

The magnitude of maximal force generally depends on five factors:

- a. The size of the physiological cross-section of the muscle,
- b. Inter-muscular coordination (coordination between the muscles involved in the movements),
- c. Intramuscular coordination (coordination within the muscles),
- d. Muscle fiber type (FT dominant ones produce more force),
- e. Motivation

20-What is quick force?

Quick force is the most force that can be produced in the least period of time. It is the capacity of the neuro-muscular system to surmount opposition in the minimal duration. Various regions of an individual's body generate distinct rapid forces.

21-What is continuity in force?

Strength endurance refers to the capacity to raise a weight for an extended duration. This may also be referred to as the organism's capacity to endure and resist tiredness during prolonged exertion.

22 - What does continuity in force depend on?

Two primary elements influence the continuation of strength. The factors are as follows: a. The magnitude of the stimulus and its range b. Muscular exhaustion.

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23-What is isometric muscle contraction?

An isometric muscular contraction is characterized by a constant muscle length throughout contraction. Iso denotes equality, whereas metric refers to measurement of length. In this kind of muscular contraction, the muscle length stays unchanged while its tension escalates. This is referred to as static muscular contraction. For instance, maintaining an upright position is accomplished by isometric muscular contraction against gravity (antigravity). Attempting to exert force against an immovable wall exemplifies this form of contraction. Wrestling is the sport characterized by the most powerful isometric contractions.

24-What is isotonic muscle contraction?

In this sort of contraction, the muscle length changes but its tension stays same. In this context, "iso" signifies equality, whereas "tonic" denotes tension. In this muscular activity, the muscle shortens (concentric) and lengthens (eccentric). It is sometimes referred to as dynamic muscular contraction. The velocity of the motion may vary.

25-What is eccentric muscle contraction?

During eccentric muscular contraction, the muscle lengthens. For instance, when an individual ascends on a pull-up bar and then begins to descend owing to gravitational forces, the biceps muscle elongates and engages. Eccentric contraction refers to a muscular activity that involves lengthening. Consequently, due to the change in muscle length, we may classify it as an isotonic contraction. Two distinct perspectives exist among the scientific community about eccentric contraction. Exercise physiologists often cannot assess eccentric contraction as an isotonic contraction. According to the sliding filament hypothesis, muscular contraction necessitates a reduction in muscle length. Exercise physiologists hold this perspective, but sports scientists have a contrary viewpoint. Sports scientists assert that this contraction is classified as isotonic due to alterations in muscle length. These studies demonstrate accelerated strength development.

26-What is concentric muscle contraction?

It is a dynamic contraction. Although the muscular tone (tension) stays constant, its length diminishes. In other terms, it is an exercise in brevity. Elevating a weight from the ground exemplifies this form of contraction. Concentric contraction is a kind of isotonic contraction due to variations in muscle length.

27-What is isotonic muscle contraction?

Isotonic contraction is a muscular activity characterized by a consistent velocity and peak tension maintained throughout the whole range of motion. The velocity stays uniform while the muscular strain varies. Isokinetic contraction requires specialized equipment. Mini-Gym or Cybex apparatus are devices capable of executing isokinetic contractions at various angles and at a constant velocity.

28 -What is auxotonic contraction?

This contraction represents a sophisticated kind of contraction. In auxotonic contraction, the pertinent muscle group first contracts isothermally, followed by concentric and eccentric contractions. In other terms, all three are seen concurrently. Auxotonic contraction refers to the simultaneous or sequential occurrence of eccentric and concentric contractions.

29-How to develop strength?

Strength enhancement is facilitated by repetition and interval techniques. These approaches include free weight training and machine-based weight training. An specialist in these topics must design a program. The repetition technique and interval method may be structured as circular training, sets (traditional weightlifting), and several other specialized formats.

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Preparation is essential prior to commencing weight training. A minimum of 7 to 8 training sessions will be conducted. Subsequent to these research, investigations into brute force (unit force, maximum force, fundamental force) may commence. These investigations should be followed by rapid strength training and sustained strength training.

30-What should be taken into consideration in weight training?

Certain factors must be considered while weight training. If these factors are disregarded, the likelihood of injury for sportsmen may increase. A proper warm-up and stretching regimen is essential prior to engaging in weight training. When using free weights in training, it is important to instruct on the technique comprehensively, including proper weight handling and breathing methods. Prior to each lift, the connection and compression points of free weights must be inspected. Athletes should unequivocally be prohibited from engaging in jest during weight training.

31-What is speed?

From a physiological standpoint, speed is defined as the capacity of muscle function to execute actions in the minimal time, contingent upon the mobility of the nervous system. Speed is a characteristic intrinsically linked to strength. Consequently, due to the swift transition between the movement stimulus and its termination, the muscular system generates a high frequency of movement appropriate for the objective. These motions can only be accomplished by the application of suitable force. Speed is a rich and intricate characteristic. It is among the most intricate topics in the field of training science. Expert assistance should unequivocally be sought in investigations conducted on this issue.

32-How to improve speed?

Speed cannot be developed without strength. To enhance an athlete's speed, it is necessary to develop strength. To enhance velocity, both maximum movement speed and maximal strength

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must be augmented. It should be noted that, whereas enhancing maximum movement speed is very challenging, increasing strength is quite straightforward. Speed has three primary components.

- a. Reaction time,
- b. Movement speed (speed of each movement)
- c. Frequency (tempo) of movement.

At this point, developing speed is achieved by developing each of these elements that make up speed separately.

33-What is durability?

The notion of endurance has several meanings. It is often assessed as the quality of fatigue resistance or the capacity to withstand fatigue. Jonathan defines endurance as the capacity to sustain a static or dynamic load for an extended duration without compromising the quality of performance. Simkin defines endurance as the duration for which an individual can sustain their strength capacity, characterized by the organism's enhanced resilience to tiredness despite the demands of exertion or unfavorable external situations. Experts have established several classes and groups for endurance. The first aspect pertains to the assessment of energy formation systems. Endurance is categorized into two types: aerobic (oxygen-dependent) endurance and anaerobic (oxygen-independent) endurance. A further division was established regarding duration, as per Harrey. This encompasses short-term, medium-term, and long-term endurance. Endurance is ultimately assessed as fundamental and specialized endurance.

34-How to develop endurance?

Training methods for developing endurance can be grouped under three main headings:

- a. Continuous loading methods,

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- b. Interval loading methods
- c. Competition and control methods.

Each of these three methods is organized and used in a different way.

35- What is coordination?

Coordination is the relationship between the central nervous system and the skeletal and muscular systems, functioning in unison to execute planned movements. Coordination is classified into two categories: general coordination and particular coordination. General coordination refers to an individual's development of diverse movement abilities, irrespective of the specific sport in which they participate. Special coordination refers to the swift, fluid, and harmonic execution of diverse and sequential motions within a certain sport.

36-What is quickness?

Quickness refers to the capacity of muscles to mobilize joints in the minimal time frame, notwithstanding external opposition from the body or its components. In other terms, speed or agility denotes the conditional and coordinative attributes of all motor activities.

37- What is skill?

Skill enables the worker to accomplish more output with comparatively less effort. Skill facilitates effective synchronization across various muscular units. Intermuscular coordination is essential for skill development. Executing a physical activity with ease is a hallmark of skilled movement. The central nervous system (CNS) transmits orders to the muscles in a precise sequence and quantity, facilitating coordinated and effective motions. An individual may exhibit heightened sensitivity and hyperactivity in response to novel stimuli. With experience, an active inhibitory mechanism emerges that aids in regulating motions, making them more

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direct and efficient. Skill fundamentally refers to the degree of coordination among the components of the locomotor system in nuanced motor activities.

38-What is mobility?

In sports science, mobility, or range of motion, is described as an individual's capacity to execute motions throughout a broad spectrum of angular values, as stated by Harre. D. Martin characterizes this idea as the capacity of joints to move optimally in all directions. In athletic training, mobility is often discussed in terms of precise movement amplitude criteria across various workouts. For instance, when seated, advance the torso forward without flexing the knees and reach the toes with the hands. The notions of flexibility and mobility are often conflated in the realm of sports. In this context, flexibility is an aspect of mobility. Flexibility pertains only to muscle. Mobility is influenced by an environment shaped by joints, muscles, ligaments, tendons, and the neurophysiological guiding mechanism.

39-What is the importance of mobility in sports?

Mobility is the fundamental need for optimal movement in both quality and quantity. Insufficient joint mobility results in the following issues: Acquiring specific movement abilities becomes unfeasible, and the process of movement learning decelerates. The likelihood of harm rises. The capacities for conditional and coordinative development diminish, and these characteristics are not completely used. In endurance sports, mobility facilitates a significant degree of movement efficiency. A restricted range of motion, or inadequate mobility, often diminishes the acceleration pathway at movement speed, resulting in a disadvantage.

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40-What is supercompensation (overcomplementation)?

During physical exercise, several chemicals in the human body are diminished owing to use. Jakowlew asserts that the depletion experienced during physical activity surpasses that which happens post-activity. This phenomenon is referred to as supercompensation.

41-What is Circuit Training?

Circuit training is a method of strength training that involves a sequence of stations, including both sport-specific and general motor skill exercises, organized consecutively for a certain duration, interspersed with designated rest intervals. Typically, it consists of a series of 8 to 12 stations. The quantity of stations is determined by evaluating age, the intended characteristic for development, and the degree of strength. The operational duration at the stations ranges from 20 to 40 seconds. The interstation rest duration is calibrated based on the athletes' power output and objectives. The rest time is established as 1:1 (i.e., equal to the loading time), 1:1.5, or 1:2. Circular training is particularly used for strength endurance or general strength exercises.

42-Why is the athlete's pulse low?

The athlete's pulse rate is decreased as a result of the beneficial adaptation of physical exercise on the cardiovascular system. At this stage, consistent physical exercise induces hypertrophy of the athlete's cardiac muscle and enlargement of the left ventricle. This therefore elevates the volume of blood the heart circulates to the body at any given moment. Consequently, when the volume pushed escalates, the quantity of pumps diminishes.

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43-What is the maximum heart rate?

The maximal pulse rate of an individual is calculated by subtracting their age from 220, as per Hollman. The pulse rate attained by the infant before to delivery is 220. A 25-year-old athlete's pulse rate may reach around 195 beats per minute.

44-What is Overtraining?

Speed training signifies persistent (long-term) weariness that is mostly psychological and typically manifests towards the conclusion of the training cycle. In this context, both musculoskeletal and neurological as well as psychological elements are significant.

45-What are the symptoms of overtraining?

Restlessness is seen in athletes experiencing overtraining symptoms. experiences fatigue easily. Reports experiencing headaches and back discomfort. perspires excessively. Dyspnea is seen. Sleep irregularities manifest. the impulse to compete diminishes. Appetite diminishes. Weight reduction may transpire. Tachycardia is seen in the morning, indicating an elevated pulse rate.

46-How to prevent overtraining?

The trainer must collaborate with the sports physician. The exercise dosage must be meticulously calibrated, the intensity should be initially decreased, sleep patterns should be optimized, and nutritional considerations should be prioritized. The training period should be made appealing for the athlete. Intermittent approvals should be granted beyond the program, or alternative activities should be included on the schedule.

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47-How is overtraining treated?

The optimal solution is to decrease the frequency of exercises and eliminate specific sessions. Moreover, walks and other hobbies have to be conducted in diverse surroundings. A sports physician should undoubtedly be collaborated with.

48 -What is regeneration (returning to normal, recovery)?

During physical exertion, the organism's internal equilibrium, known as homeostasis, is disturbed. The intensity and duration of the exercise induce changes in several resting physiological parameters of the body, such as heart rate, blood pressure, respiratory rate, and blood pH. Upon the cessation of physical activity, each of these variables reverts to baseline levels, namely the resting values, over varying durations. This phenomenon is referred to as normalization, recuperation, or regeneration. The standard duration fluctuates based on the intensity and length of the physical activity. The kind of relaxation and the degree of fitness also influence this duration. Research indicates that active rest reduces the duration of the healing time.

49-What is sportive technique?

Sport technique refers to the most efficient and cost-effective execution of a certain athletic activity in the most challenging manner. Djakov describes excellence in sports technique as the ability to execute the movement patterns of athletic exercises with economy and precision under the most challenging competitive situations, hence attaining maximum efficiency.

50-What is sport tactics?

Zech posits that sports tactics are strategic actions formulated in response to an opponent's performance and the prevailing environmental circumstances in both individual and team tournaments.

WARMING

Warming up is an essential component of athletic exercises. It is well recognized that all sports training and tournaments start with a warm-up exercise. This section outlines the impact of warming up on performance and its influence on sports injuries. Warming up is the main component of athletic action. Nevertheless, we typically believe that this topic is not accorded sufficient significance for many reasons. Presented here are questions and answers that we consider significant about the warm-up process. For more information on the topic, you may consult our sources and also contact us via email. We shall endeavor to address your inquiries within the limits of our expertise.

1-What is Warm up?

The comprehensive set of physical and mental exercises conducted before to a competition or training session to attain optimal performance is referred to as warming up. In summary, warming up entails the comprehensive preparation of the body for competition or training. When assessing the idea of warming up, the warming up event should first be considered in two dimensions. These aspects pertain to global warming and localized warming. General warming up refers to the comprehensive preparation of the body, achieved via active or passive methods, prior to a competition or training session. Local warming up refers to the use of active or passive techniques aimed at warming specific muscle groups during rehabilitation after sports injuries or impairments, or in preparation for training post-rehabilitation.

2-What are the benefits of warming up?

In our view, warming up is the main component of any athletic endeavor. Consequently, we want to examine this subject in some depth. In examining sports fields, we often encounter three categories of athletes with distinct warming-up practices. There are three athlete groups: the first warms up independently with particular exercises; the second engages in a shared group

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warm-up program; and the third warms up under a coach's supervision. Athletes perceive warm-up in three distinct ways based on their educational background, athletic experience, professionalism, and performance level. For many athletes, the warm-up phase serves as an opportunity to evade training or competition. For many athletes, warming up is the most critical and essential component of training or competition, and they place significant emphasis on this practice. Certain athletes see warming up as an essential component of their responsibilities prior to training or competition. Fundamentally, warming up is the main component of both training and athletic competition preparation. Adequate warm-up enhances both aerobic and anaerobic energy output. Research indicates that muscle strength increases with adequate warm-up in relation to neuro-muscular activity. Warmed-up muscles exhibit increased flexibility and enhanced contraction speed. Warming up reduces the response time of nerves and muscles. The enhancement of muscle flexibility due to warming up facilitates increased joint amplitudes (range of motion). Joint mobility is enhanced with warming up. Moreover, target orientation (precision) and movement coordination may be enhanced with warm-up exercises. Generally, warming up enhances endurance, speed, strength, leaping capability, and flexibility. Simultaneously, a significant health benefit of warming up is its capacity to reduce the risk of sports-related injuries, including those affecting muscles, ligaments, and tendons. Consequently, when warming up is assessed on a muscular level, two primary impacts are often observed:

A prophylactic impact of the incident in averting impairment.

B- The impact of the event in enhancing worker performance.

An examination of sports literature revealed that a well-timed and executed warm-up consistently has beneficial impacts on performance.

3-How long should the warm-up period be?

The duration of the warm-up phase varies according on the sport. The literature indicates a duration ranging from 10 to 30 minutes for this interval. This duration differs between team

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sports and individual sports. Furthermore, while establishing the warm-up duration, one must consider the surroundings of the competition or training venue, the ambient temperature, and the timing of the event. Certain research indicates that the warm-up duration should include 20-30 percent of the whole training session.

4-What are the warm-up methods?

In sports literature, two categories of warm-up techniques are identified. These include both active and passive warm-up techniques. An active warm-up strategy involves engaging in physical activities prior to training or competition. The passive warm-up approach utilizes numerous instruments for the healing of sports injuries and is used by athletes who have just finished therapy prior to training. This passive warm-up employs different electrical physical therapy equipment, baths, showers, whirlpool baths, massages with standard or specialized creams, and other physical therapy techniques.

5- What are the warm-up methods?

Warm-up techniques are categorized into casual and formal types. Informal warm-ups are exercises that do not fall under a certain category, such as jogging, running, or calisthenics. Formal warm-ups include motions tailored to the unique discipline of the sport. Movements such as shooting in basketball, serving in volleyball, executing serves or playing in squash, and passing in football are recognized formal warm-up techniques.

6-What should be started with warming up?

The warm-up should start with an informal segment, followed by a formal one. There are two perspectives on this topic for casual warm-up. The initial perspective is that the primary activity during a warm-up including unstructured, non-branch-specific motions should be stretching exercises. The other perspective asserts that jogging should unequivocally precede stretching.

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The literature and studies evaluated provide no definitive explanation on this issue. The preference here fluctuates based on the trainer's practices. Subsequent to the casual warm-up, the official warm-up pertinent to that branch is conducted. The last stage of the warm-up should have structured motions.

7 - How long should the stretching period be?

The time of stretching varies based on the specific kind of stretching technique used. Bob Anderson states that this length ranges from 4 seconds to 60 seconds. For instance, the duration is 15-30 seconds for the calf muscle and Achilles tendon, but it is 5 seconds for the neck muscles.

8- What does pain indicate during stretching?

A multitude of individuals engage in stretching to enhance their flexibility. Consequently, while stretching, they extend to their maximum capacity. The muscle undergoing stretching becomes rigid. If discomfort occurs while stretching, one should cease the activity. Numerous sportsmen often stretch to the point of discomfort. This idea arises from the erroneous reasoning that excessive stretching would enhance their flexibility more rapidly. This is inaccurate, since the discomfort experienced when stretching signifies microtrauma within that muscle group. Overstretching results in microscopic tissue damage and scarring. If the scars are permanent, they will diminish muscular suppleness and induce discomfort in the muscle. At this stage, the muscle fibers supplant the inelastic fibers with less elasticity, while the thick scars obstruct blood circulation in the tissues, so disrupting the afferent nerve receptors. Consequently, it inflicts more damage on the pertinent muscle fibers and the surrounding muscle tissues. Any overstretching will lead to inadequate blood circulation. Consequently, the objective is diverted. Excessive stretching in pursuit of greater flexibility may have counterproductive results. The pliability of that muscle group diminishes. Ultimately, any excessive stretching is perilous and futile. The discomfort experienced when stretching signifies the onset of this negativity.

9- What is the difference between stretching and flexibility?

Stretching and flexibility are ideas that are sometimes conflated. In stretching, the muscles are maintained in a static posture for a specified duration. During stretching, the muscle is continuously relaxed and constricted. Stretching is an exercise method used to enhance muscular flexibility.

Is a warm-down essential?

Post-training or competition cooldown is a crucial and essential process. It must be completed at the conclusion of each training session. The creature requires both cooling and warming. Cooling down is a method of active recovery. Lactic acid, a fatigue-inducing compound present in muscles and blood, is eliminated more rapidly via active rest. Consequently, healing is facilitated more expeditiously.

Shooting or committing a foul at the conclusion of basketball practice, executing a corner kick or penalty kick at the end of football training, and serving at the conclusion of volleyball practice function as cool-down techniques. Moreover, running or stretching may be used as a means of cooling down. The only crucial aspect to remember is the need of cooling down. The cooling duration must be no less than 10 minutes.

SPORTS INJURIES

Sports injuries often pertain directly to the physician's concerns. Consequently, this part will only include statistics, fundamental facts, and definitions. It is essential to remember that in the case of a sports injury or impairment, the first step is to seek consultation with a specialized physician.

GENERAL INFORMATION

A research done from 1983 to 1987 at the Ege University Medical Faculty Orthopedics and Traumatology Clinic analyzed 1560 instances of sports injuries that presented to the clinic during a five-year period. It was shown that 22 percent of the injuries were contusions and 20 percent were fractures. The lower extremities (groin, leg, knee, ankle, foot) was identified as the most often damaged region, accounting for 60 percent of injuries. Overuse injuries were identified as the most prevalent issue faced by athletes.

Dr. Girgin asserts that football players often encounter abrasions, contusions, superficial bruises, uncomplicated muscle strains, muscular cramps, minor ankle sprains, simple epistaxis, transient injuries to the lumbar and dorsal regions, cervical traumas, and injuries to the brow and cranial areas. Dagarov and Slanchev assert in their study that football players often encounter distortions (sprains), contusions (bruises), meniscal injuries, and muscle tears (ruptures). A common injury among football players is soreness in the inner-upper region of the thigh, namely in the groin area. The condition arises from excessive tension or stretching of the muscles that draw the leg inside, leading to the rupture or strain of the tendons (ligaments) connected to the groin (pelvic bone) of the muscle at its attachment sites to the bone.

Basketball players may have soft tissue injuries (bruises, muscle or fiber tears, hemorrhaging, muscular rigidity, cramps, etc.), joint injuries (ligament tears, meniscus injuries, ankle sprains, finger joint strains, lumbar strains, shoulder dislocations), fractures, and significant injuries. In runners, the most prevalent injuries seen were muscle and tendon strains, overuse injuries, joint and ligament problems, and meniscus lesions. The causes include training faults (abrupt increases in distance and speed), anatomical problems, footwear, and terrain. Soft tissue injuries occur more often in weightlifting. Injuries may affect the trunk and rib cage muscles, back muscles, waist, and wrists of weightlifters.

In boxing, the facial region sustains the greatest injuries. The primary objective of punches in boxing is the face and jaw. Consequently, facial injuries may range from minor contusions to severe fractures and critical damage to facial structures. The predominant injuries are eyebrow lacerations. Furthermore, subsequent and protracted injuries include fractures, collapses, and deviations of the nasal concha in boxers. Temporary loss of consciousness is prevalent in

boxing. This persists for varying durations contingent upon the impact's degree, as well as the athlete's stamina and expertise. Both temporary and permanent brain damage can occur in boxing.

Judokas may exhibit soft tissue injuries to the wrist and fingers, superficial abrasions on the knee, intra- and extra-articular hematomas, as well as lesions of the ligaments, capsule, and meniscus, in addition to numerous head traumas.

Skiers experience ankle injuries, leg injuries, knee joint injuries, brain traumas, spine injuries, frostbite, and UV burns.

1-What is a sports injury?

Sports injuries refer to many types of harm sustained during athletic activity. Groh states that the likelihood of injury among athletes is one in 4,000, whereas the fatality rate is one in 40,000. The likelihood of experiencing a significant accident is one in 40 individuals. The sports with the highest incidence of injuries include football at 10%, wrestling at 6%, handball and boxing at 3%, athletics at 1%, and skiing at 0.5%.

2-What are the causes of sports injuries?

causes contributing to sports injuries may be categorized into two classifications: endogenous (personal) and exogenous (environmental) causes.

Personal factors: Physical impairments (muscle weakness, joint restrictions, inadequate flexibility), fatigue and overexertion, anatomical anomalies, psychological influences (risk acceptance, excessive ambition), inadequately rehabilitated injuries, muscle rigidity (resulting from overexertion or infection), age, and gender.

Environmental factors: Substandard sports technique, insufficient training, usage of inferior equipment, environmental circumstances (weather), terrain, and noncompliance with regulations.

3-What is the seriousness of the sports injury?

To comprehend the severity of a sports injury, six fundamental facts must be assessed. The pertinent information include the mechanism of injury, the treatment approach and length, the period of absence from the sport, the number of workdays missed, any permanent impairment, and the financial implications. The severity of a sports injury is understood by considering and evaluating these facts one by one. If it resulted in 1-7 days away from the sport, it is classified as MILD; if it resulted in 8-21 days away, it is classified as MODERATE; and if it resulted in more than 21 days away, it is classified as SEVERE.

4-What are the general rules for preventing sports injuries?

Initially, it is important to do frequent health assessments of the sportsmen. The checks disclose the athlete's present status at the season's commencement. Deficiencies are identified, and appropriate procedures to rectify them are implemented in accordance with the physician's recommendations. The identified deficits pertain to physiological metrics, physical fitness, and direct health-related issues. Inadequate warm-up is a critical factor contributing to the incidence of sports injuries. Consequently, significant emphasis should be placed on warm-up and particularly stretching activities.

Post-exercise cooling is also crucial in this context. Post-activity cooling is also essential. Cooling down activities must be performed after any activity. Engaging in stretching exercises post-activity is as helpful and significant as doing them before to the activity.

5-What is muscle fatigue?

It is a condition characterized by the accumulation of waste products (such as lactic acid) during physical exertion, leading to diminished energy reserves. It is often associated with physical

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capability (training background). It typically concludes with the elimination of waste products and replenishment of reserves within 1-2 hours post-exercise.

6- What is muscle pain (soreness)?

It refers to muscular soreness that persists for hours or days after strenuous or atypical activity. The affected muscles are uncomfortable, sometimes bloated, and firm. It is referred to as "weakness" among athletes. It primarily manifests in inexperienced athletes after intense and unfamiliar muscular contractions. This often results from cellular injury in muscles that engage in negative activity (braking function), particularly after atypically intense eccentric contractions and activities (such as downhill movements). It resolves spontaneously over time. It does not need a cessation of physical activity.

7- What is Strain?

It is the elongation of the muscle beyond its capacity for extension. Muscle tension is indicated when this limit is surpassed. Numerous muscle fibers are structurally compromised. Despite the presence of discomfort in the damaged region during movement and stretching, there is no substantial loss of strength or notable bleeding. The integrity of the muscle is maintained.

8-What is a partial muscle tear?

Partial muscle tears happen from maximal contraction or stretching. Muscle contraction results in discomfort, considerable hemorrhage, and swelling (hematoma).

9-What is muscle (complete) tear?

Muscle rupture happens abruptly and is followed by intense pain in the affected muscle groups. Muscle integrity is compromised, accompanied by significant hemorrhaging, edema

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(hematoma), discomfort, and diminished strength and mobility. Muscle tears may be attributed to two factors:

- a. Lack of coordination during maximum contraction.
- b. Abrupt contraction of a rigid (extensible) muscle against substantial opposition.

10-What are the factors that predispose to muscle tear?

These factors are:

- a. Inadequate training and warm-up.
- b. Inadequate rehabilitation of previous injury.
- c. Scar tissue resulting from a previous injury.
- d. Overtraining, fatigue, infection.
- e. Inadequate soft tissue elasticity.
- f. A muscle with poor extensibility.

11- What should be done in case of muscle tear?

The activity must be terminated. Activities that may exacerbate bleeding and injury, such as vigorous inspection, massage, heat application, and similar interventions that stress the affected tissue, should be avoided. Apply cold, and use a protective bandage or splint until you reach the closest healthcare facility or physician.

12-When should cold therapy be applied?

Cold therapy is a primary therapeutic modality used in the acute management of sports injuries. The objective is to manage hemorrhage and inflammation effectively. Cold treatment should start immediately after the injury and persist throughout the first 48-72 hours.

13 -What is the benefit of cold therapy?

Cold application diminishes blood circulation to the affected region. Consequently, the translocation of chemicals that exacerbate hemorrhage and nociception/damage to the affected region is diminished. Cold treatment must be administered after all sports injuries until the cessation of swelling and bleeding.

14-How should cold treatment be done?

Cold therapy may be administered using ice packs every two hours, with each application not exceeding 20 minutes. The total application duration in a day must not surpass 2 hours (6 intervals of 20 minutes each). When using deep-frozen gels for cold therapy, a duration of 15 minutes is adequate rather than 20 minutes. The skin in the region where cold is administered must be shielded from direct touch.

15-What is the importance of bandaging?

During the acute period of the injury, it aids in minimizing hemorrhage and tissue damage by enhancing circulation. During the later stages of the injury, bandaging assists the athlete in safeguarding the affected tissue or joint by serving as a conscious or unconscious reminder of the damage. Bandaging alone does not safeguard a tissue or joint from potential injury.

16-What is a contusion?

It is the compression of soft tissues between the impact surface and the bone due to direct trauma. It is marked by contusions (blood buildup), edema, and discomfort due to vascular injury and fluid extravasation.

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17--What is hematoma?

It is the accumulation of blood extravasated from a vessel in a specific region due to vascular injury resulting from trauma.

18-What is Myositis ossificans (Muscle ossification)?

One of the adverse outcomes of muscle injuries is the deposition of calcium on the blood clot, resembling bone, due to untreated muscle tears and bleeding. In summary, it is a common complication of inadequately managed muscular strains (contusion and/or tear). This condition results in discomfort, diminished strength, and reduced flexibility in the muscle, leading to functional impairment. The likelihood of rupture in the pertinent muscle is elevated.

19 -What is the role of massage in sports injuries?

Massage prepares the muscles for optimal performance and safeguards them against injury. It facilitates the expedited removal of fatigue-inducing chemicals from the muscular region post-training or competition. It is used for medicinal reasons. The physiological benefits of massage include the regulation of blood and lymphatic circulation.

It allows the athlete to experience improved subjective well-being via stimulation and relaxation.

20-What is a joint mouse?

Joint mouse refers to the detachment of a cartilage fragment for whatever cause, which then becomes mobile inside the joint. It induces discomfort and impairs functionality inside the joint.

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21-What is a Fracture?

A fracture is the loss of a bone's anatomical integrity caused by trauma or other factors. The interruption of bone continuity may manifest as a little fracture, a significant separation, or many fragments.

22-Why does a fracture occur?

Fractures may be induced by pushing, pulling, compressive, or shearing forces. Furthermore, the decline in tissue resilience resulting from illness, exhaustion, or senescence leads to bone fractures.

23-What is a fissure?

A crack is fundamentally a kind of fracture. In this fissure, the continuity of the bone manifests only as a slender line.

24 -What is Distortion (Spraining)?

A sprain is an injury to a joint. There are three categories of sprains. A first-degree sprain involves a little tension of the joint. Local tenderness is present. Joint mobility is within normal limits. A second-degree sprain involves partial tears in the joint ligaments. There is a little degree of atypical joint mobility, hemorrhaging, and edema. A third-degree sprain involves total tearing of the ligaments. There is significant aberrant joint mobility. There is abrupt, intense edema, hemorrhage, and discomfort.

Conclusion

As players endeavor to expand their physical limits, the intricate equilibrium between intensive training and injury avoidance emerges as a vital issue in sports performance. The intrinsic risk of injury is a constant concern that sports programs and healthcare experts must address, since the repercussions of such incidents may significantly affect an athlete's career path and general health. A key factor leading to sporting injuries is the training regimen's nature. Training, whether for competition or general fitness, may impose significant stress on the musculoskeletal system, increasing the risk of injury. Athletes striving to enhance their strength, speed, and endurance often exert their bodies to the extreme, resulting in weakened tissues that cannot endure the tremendous demands imposed upon them. Kraemer et al. (2009) This dynamic is most apparent in sports characterized by explosive movements, high-impact activities, and repeated stress, including numerous team sports, track and field events, and fighting disciplines. The significance of appropriate training methodologies and injury prevention measures is paramount.

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